

External Factors that Affects the Impulsive Buying Behavior in Karachi

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Abstract

In recent years, the patterns of Impulse Buying is showing dramatically change, as a result of the advancement in economic era, technology, and overall development, Consumers are progressively shifting towards wholesale centers & the supermarkets. Hence, all these developments and changes in the consumers buying patterns create a need to identify the elements, which results in stimulating Impulse Buying Behavior among consumers in metropolitan cities. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify external elements (includes sales personnel behavior, in-store display, window display and in-store Promotional signage) that affect the impulse purchase behavior in Karachi. In order to achieve the objectives, the survey had been conducted using a Self-Administered Questionnaire & the data was collected from 230 respondents who preferred to shop at supermarkets & malls. Using the correlation & regression techniques, the results of present study showed that all four factors have positive correlation with impulse buying behavior of consumers & all these factors excluding sales personal behavior have direct impact on impulse buying. This research will be beneficial for the marketers and store owners to create effective strategies regarding Sales personnel behavior, in-store display, Window Display, and in-store Promotional signage to attract more and more customers and in return increase in their sales turnover.

Keywords: Consumer Behavior, Interactions, Exchanges, Consumer Buying Process, Impulse Buying Behavior

1. Background

In preceding five years, as a result of massive growth in the wholesale & retail sectors & the advent of supermarkets or malls has vigorously influenced the behavior of the consumer i.e. fashioning a new community of passionate & enthusiastic consumers from the upper & middle classes. One can witnessed that the increase in the number and different setups of the retail outlets would result in delivering a value added shopping experience to the consumers i.e. consumers are buying the products zealously, avoiding the fact that inflation has made their life miserable. One reason for this massive growth might be that the consumer feels more secure in these outlets because of efficient security system that the conventional shopping centers lack. These stores are characterized with a self-service that provide ease in the form systematized walkways, larger product variety, comfortable push cart system & a sole exit point. In Karachi, Super-stores like Hyperstar, Metro Cash & Cary, Imtiaz Store, Naheed's, Ebco, My Super Store etc. are live example for increasing the new shopping experience. (Bokhari, 2013). In recent years, impulsive buying has been increased due to the economic development & self-conscience. Consumers are progressively shifting towards wholesale centers & the local supermarkets. However, the explanations for this explosion are hard to trace. There must be a range of certain stimuli or factors that influence the shift in the purchase decisions of the consumers.

Impulsive Buying behavior is defined as the unintended decision to spend money on a product or service, before the actual purchase. Impulsive purchasing is generally considered to be an important part of the buying behavior patterns of the consumer. Impulse purchase is the consequence of exposure towards a product/service, and the decision to purchase it is made on the spot. Whenever a customer goes for any sort of shopping in a particular store without any plan for purchases, they are sometime, exposed to a stimulus, which triggers the urge of the customer to buy a certain product. When such an exposure occurs to a customer, he doesn't actually search or evaluate whether this decision of purchases would be right or wrong, instead he/she just go for the purchases (Parboteeah 2005; based on Piron, 1991:514). Most of procurements are being made in the store's premises. It is the premises, which triggers the buying urge of the customer and makes him force to make purchases of the product (Paco, writer of Why We Buy: The Science of Shopping: 1999). The progress of electronic-commerce & the emergent customer-orientation of several cultures across the globe offer escalating events for the consumers to purchase impulsively. Many authors promote that the shoppers procure on impulse pattern & are having the ability to grow more with the introduction of novel technologies like Internet and TV shopping channel, which carries eye-catching design and posters. Furthermore, the strategy of 24-hour convenience stores have not only increased the impulse purchase behavior but also increased the accessibility of the goods and services. Since several decades, marketers & researchers are always interested in examining the phenomenon of impulse purchasing but most of the researches conducted are focused towards developed countries. Its importance is identified by marketing and research firms all over the globe and it has been

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widely researched during the past 60 years". In early time's researches on impulsive purchase included DuPont Consumer Habits Studies especially in 1940 to 1960s and researches by Patterson in 1960s that was funded by an advertising institute. Past researches have suggested that around 80% of the purchases in the US are made impulsively. In another study, statistical figure stood 90% with respect to impulsive buying behavior.

Lawton, Kleban, Rajogopal, and Dean, (1992), McConatha et al.,(1994), Siegel, (1985) in their researches argued that aged consumers Posses greater regulation and they are less likely to get emotional appeals as compared to young consumers. This finding shows that when the shoppers tend to be aged, there urge for impulsive buying behavior patterns decreases. I.e. there is a negative relation between age and impulse buying behavior. Developed States such as USA, UK, Canada etc., have extensively researched on the topic of impulsive buying behavior. However, the customers living in developed countries are different in all aspects of life from the customers living in developing countries. (I.e. the impulse buying tends to be quite different apart from one consumer to another on various elements like perceptions, insights, lifestyles, personality traits and so on). In general, majority of the research has been conducted on internal factors including demographics factors like (age, income, gender etc.), cultural factors, and psychographic factors (emotions, mood, attitude etc.). According to Usman Ghani and Farzand Ali Jan, (2010) The association between demographic elements and the impulse purchase habits of metropolitan city's customers of Pakistan shows that age alone has a substantial -ve relationship with impulse purchasing habits of customers. This means that youth are more involved in impulsive purchases compared to aged customers. In Pakistan, these studies are limited to the internal factor, which sometimes does not portray the clear image of impulse buying patterns. Therefore, it creates a need of identifying the impact of external factors on impulse buying behavior.

"In the recent years, the pattern of impulse buying has been changed dramatically as a result of the advancement in economic era, technology, and overall development in metropolitan cities of Pakistan especially in Karachi, where new shopping patterns in malls, exclusive outlets of brands, superstores and one stop shop solution has been introduced. "All these developments have changed the buying patterns of the consumers "have simultaneously increased the revenue base of the organizations" Hence, all these developments and changes in the consumers buying patterns create a need to identify those Elements, which results in the stimulating Impulse Buying Behavior among consumers in metropolitan cities. Generally, internal factors tend to be different for every consumer, depending on diversified cultural, personality traits, lifestyles, moods. Hence, it is difficult to identify what really causes impulsive behavior This research will be beneficial for the marketers and store owners to create effective strategies regarding Sales personnel behavior, in-store display, Window Display, and in-store Promotional signage to attract more and more customers and in return increase in their sales turnover. In addition, this study will be beneficial for the students of Pakistan to relate their theoretical concepts of consumer impulse buying behavior and to apply the same in practical world.

2. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior consist of the feelings and thoughts that individuals experience, and the steps that they are likely to accomplish in consumption stages (Peter & Olson, 2008: 5).It, explains the way in which the consumer behaves while interacting with a certain stimuli. Stimuli', which are likely to influence the feelings, actions, and thoughts; what affects the behavior of consumer accordingly. It is therefore significant to identify that behavior of consumer is quite dynamic and its determination requires a deep study along with thorough research. Internet for example has transformed the way information is explored by individuals about products/services. The fact that shoppers' trends and their surroundings are continuously changing which rather amplify the importance for conducting ongoing consumer studies/research and its analysis by marketing agencies to keep in touch with the important ongoing trends. According to (Kotler et al., 1999) Shopper and their purchasing behavior are influenced by some motivations coming from the exterior surrounding i.e., (PEST Analysis) and from grouping of constructs, namely the 4 marketing P's i.e., Product, Promotion, Place and Price. The Dynamic Nature of consumer behavior helps to develop marketing strategies however; still it is a challenging task to determine the accuracy of consumer behavior in order to match with the marketing strategies. "The fundamental query for marketing agencies is: how shoppers respond to several stimuli that the firm may use as a tool for to engage customers in the buying process? The firm that actually comprehends how customers will respond to different features of the product, marketing appeals & prices tends to obtain competitive edge over rivals." (Kotler et al., 1999) As a result, companies have in progress to examine the connection among marketing stimulus and customer reaction. The model of consumer actions (Kotler et al., 1999) has been established in order to cater and assist the marketing strategist to develop marketing strategies for future profitability of the organizations (Rossi & Cristina, 2012). According to J. Paul Peter & Olson (2007) Consumer Behavior involves interaction and exchanges

3. Consumer Behavior Requires Interactions

Behavior of consumer comprises of communications between thoughts, feelings, and actions, of the people and the entire external surroundings. Thus, marketing agencies need to understand what do the brands and products actually mean to customers, and what are those elements, which affect the customer to go for purchasing the products/services. The more marketers have knowledge and research about how such communications would affect a customer, target markets of same customers, and society at a broad level, the better they can be able to fulfill consumer needs, wants and create positive value for them. (J. & Olson, 2007) Such a behavior requires Lower participation in purchasing; since majority of the goods are purchased at a lower cost; which needs little effort and time; i.e., purchased almost automatically. This involves buying goods seldom. In this regard, consumers require information about unaware maker in a familiar category product. This needs a reasonable interval of time for collecting of information. Decision making is quite complex and it requires a high involvement, since the products are unfamiliar, expensive and are infrequently bought by the customers. Due to such elements, it involves Great degree of psychological/performance/economic risk. Examples, for such goods include cars, homes, computers, education. Although some these goods are familiar however due to their expensive nature, they involve quite a great degree of time in making purchase decision. In this regard, consumers tend to seek Info from the firms, networks, kin, & store workers etc.

4. Consumer Behavior Requires Exchanges

Behavior of consumer includes exchanges among human beings. In other words people forgo something to obtain the next best alternative i.e., opportunity cost Majority of consumer behavior includes people forgoing their money and other valuables to get products/services, i.e., barter among purchasers and vendors. In fact, to help the society and establish exchanges by creating and applying marketing tactics is the objective of marketing, which ultimately leads to the overall long term profitability of the organization (J. & Olson, 2007).

5. Consumer Buying Process

Generally, whenever a customer enters in a shopping mall or any superstore to buy goods and services he/she is sub-consciously is following Six Stages of Consumer Buying Decision Process especially (For complex decisions). In actuality purchase decision process, neither always includes all six steps, nor do all of the decision processes lead to a final purchase. Generally, it varies from customer to customer based on various scenarios Berkowitz, E.N. et al (1994).

6. Process of Impulse Buying Behavior

Impulse buying process is different from intended or scheduled purchase that is defined in the model of Churchill and Peter's (1998). By omitting various phases, i.e. recognition of need, getting information, and evaluation of alternative, and reclassifying the stimulating factors, Kim (2003) explained the Impulse Buying Process as follows:

The process initiate with the product wakefulness followed by surfing for a product having lack of intent to buy a product. As consumers search the product, an Internal cues (such as mood/desire/need, cognitive or affective evaluation, hedonic pleasure) & External cues (such as in-store form display, visual merchandising, window display,

promotional offers, floor merchandising) stimulates the customers' to purchase it instantly without getting information & evaluate substitutes. At that stage of impulse buying procedure, the buyer feels a desirable urge to buy a product irrespective of their prior intent. Maclinnis & Price (1987) & Sherry (1990) identify that after purchasing the product instantaneously the buyers could practice negative or positive significances by *post-purchase evaluation*. In effect, certain customers are dissatisfied with the purchase, but most of them are satisfied after the impulse purchase. Base on the '*affect*' vs. '*cognition*' that is present in the decision process the Impulse Buying process is categorized into four different types (Stern, 1962) In the same vein, on the basis of Stern (1962) separation, Han *et al.* (1991) categorized the Impulse Buying Behavior for 'apparel' products into four types as follows: Pure impulse buying, Reminded Impulse Buying, Fashion Oriented impulse buying and Planned Impulse Buying.

Wansink (1994) said that the purchase performance of consumers is influenced by internal as well as the external factors. Rook and Fisher (1995) said that impulse purchase is regularly provocation focused. On the other hand, Iyer (1989) said that enhancing the exposure to certain external factors consequences the increase of impulsive buying of a product. Chen (2001) identifies four factors that can influence the consumer to purchase impulsively. These includes *internal elements* (i.e. personality, lifestyle, emotion, time pressure and money), *external factors* (i.e. buying frequency, advertising & promotions, store displays, store atmosphere & the retailers). While *demographic variables* (i.e. income, age, gender, literacy, profession, income of household marital status, and social status) & *buying behavior* (i.e. price, payment, the time available for purchasing), However most of the researchers classify the factors as either '*internal*' or '*external*'.

Source: Adapted from Kim (2003)

7. Internal Factors of Impulse Buying

According to Kacen and Lee (2002) internal elements of impulse buying, emphasize on examining the inner stimuli and features of the buyer that triggers them to do purchasing of product impulsively. These factors may include personality traits of consumer that define the tendency of their impulse purchase behavior, the emotional states, demographic factors, cultural factors and the normative evaluation of consumers that stimulate them to purchase the item impulsively. Gardner & Rook, (1988), Rook (1987) & Rook & Gardner (1993) studies on Consumer Behavior consider '*Affect*' or '*Mood*' as a variable which encourage the Impulse Buying, whereas the studies on Consumer Behavior by Piron (1991), Thompson, Locander, & Pollio (1990), Hirschman (1980) & Holbrook & Hirschman (1982), recognize that consumers' impulse purchasing satisfy their '*Hedonic Needs*' including pleasure, novelty & surprise. Bowers' (1973) observed that consumer avoid and build situations in response with their needs. Anglin, Morgan and Stoltman (1999) study said that consumer ignore retail settings which are hectic or obtrusive. Babin (2001) stated that emotions or feelings can have a greater impact on the consumer purchase intention & spending on products & these emotions can be precise to certain stuffs, which depend on structures of the products, consumers' self-interest, ability to evaluate items & the importance of the products. Cobb and Hoyer (1986) researched on impulse buying identify that with respect to the personnel responses & the opinions the 'shopping lifestyles' are the causes

that inspire the purchase of a product. Impulse buying behavior & shopping lifestyle are closely associated just in the case of impulse buyers (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998).

8. External Factors of Impulse Buying

External cues or stimuli refer to the four P's tools that are under the control of marketers who can stimulate the consumers to purchase the product impulsively (Youn & Faber, 2000). Visually encountering variables for instance 'promotional offers' triggers the consumer to indulge in impulse purchasing (Dholakia, 2000 & Rook, 1987), these tools not only attract prospect customers but also stimulate *up- and cross-selling* of complimentary products to current or new customers. Due to the changing behavior & adoptive nature of consumers' expectations & preferences, the 'specific locations' & 'retail situation' can have an impact on both in-store responses & choice of prospect store of a consumer (Hausman, 2000). For example, Darden *et al.*'s (1983) study on impulse buying behavior had found that consumers' store choice & the store's physical attractiveness had highly correlated instead of quality of commodities, general price level, & selection. In contrast, Stern (1962) reported that the products, which are less expensive, are purchased spontaneously. Analyzing the impulse buying behavior of a consumer who shops at the Shopping Malls Jayaraman Munusamy (2010), examine the influence of store ambiance, customer's service, store communications, sales promotion & the mood of the consumer on impulse buying & found that store environment, customer's service & the mood of the customer have substantially positive association with the impulse buying. More & more attraction of a consumer with salespersons would probably increase the impulse buying. Peck and Childers (2006). Attitude, values, & norms of the consumers are changing slowly that can alter their views with respect to surroundings & lifestyles Crawford and Melewar (2003). Because of the trend of fashion & fad, the consumers purchase the products having new design /style, instantly and spontaneously in order to express their self-identity. According to Kathleen & Ronald (2007) study, the representatives buy or spend more on those products instantly which they feel are limited or depleted. Jeffrey and Hodge (2007) conducted a research & identify that online system as one of the factor that influence the people to buy impulsively, he concluded that the time spent on website & impulse purchasing are directly correlated i.e. the store location (online) has a greater influence on the buying behavior of the consumer.

9. Theoretical Framework

Generally, internal factors tend to be different for every consumer, depending on diversified cultural, personality traits, lifestyles, moods. Hence, it is difficult to identify what really causes impulsive behavior. Therefore, the objective of this research is to explore External Causes that affects the impulsive purchase behavior in Karachi. In our literature, a study conducted by JIYEON KIM (2003), explained the association b/w the impulse buying behavior of college students. Furthermore, he had categories the visual merchandising (*i.e. promotional signage & in-store display*) & he found that there is a substantial positive association among Promotional Signage, In-store display and the Impulse purchasing Behavior i.e. these two factors serves as a stimuli that motivates the consumers to purchase the product

impulsively. Darden *et al.*'s (1983) study on impulse buying behavior had found that consumers' store choice & the *store's physical attractiveness* are highly correlated. Diamond and Diamond, (1996), state that nowadays the retailers consider *window display* as the most important variable to attract the attention of by-standers & ultimately converting them into prospect customers. Mohd. Rumzi Taushif, Manisha Gupta (2013) study of "*factors affecting impulse buying behavior of consumers at malls (Delhi)*" found that in retail environment the *atmospheric cues* are considered as effective stimuli that trigger the consumer to purchase the product impulsively.

"*Assessing Effective Elements on Customer Impulse Purchasing Behavior*" by Alireza Karbasivar and Hasti Yarahmadi (2011), indicate that promotional approaches (i.e cash discount) & the in-store form display play a vital role to stimulate the consumers to purchase the apparel products impulsively. Analyzing the impulse buying behavior of a consumer who shops at the Shopping Malls Jayaraman Munusamy (2010) examined the influence of store ambiance, customer's service, store communications, sales promotion & the mood of the consumer on impulse buying & found that among all, store environment, customer's service & the mood of the customer have substantially positive association with the impulse buying. While Peck and Childers (2006) stated that more & more attraction of a consumer with salesmen would probably increase the impulse buying.

Ho1: sales personnel behavior has no significant control over Impulsive Purchase Patterns.

Ho2: In-store Display has no significant control over Impulsive Purchase Patterns.

Ho3: Window Display has no significant control over Impulsive Purchase Patterns.

Ho4: In-store Promotional Signage has no significant control over impulse buying Behavior.

10. Methodology

Impulsive Purchasing activities defined as the unintentional judgment to purchase a goods/ service, which made before the actual acquisition. Our *Study philosophical Idea* style is the *positivisms* as most of the researcher had already worked on this topic in the context of developed countries and we are verifying this existing knowledge in context of the metropolitan city of Pakistan i.e. *Karachi*. Only the external factors are selected from the model to gauge their effect in the context of Pakistan hence it would be an *inductive approach*. Because of Area of our research, we have progressed over and done an *Explanatory study*. We had followed the *mono-method* and our research would be concentrated on the Quantitative method. *Time limit* of our study is cross-sectional since we have narrow period to comprehend and submit our exploration. In-order to generate vivid image concerning the several goals of the study we would float survey to consumers for our data collection. The focus of the study is to pinpoint the external variables affecting buyers' impulsiveness for this objective numerous publications were studied in order to write down the intro and background of the study. Many researcher had conducted the research on this topic in the context of developed countries and we are verifying this existing knowledge in context of the metropolitan city of developing country Pakistan i.e. Karachi. Judgmental sampling technique was used due to easy availability to the researcher. SPSS was used to analyze the data. To test the hypotheses of this research, data was gathered from the first-hand information to audience of metropolitan city of Karachi who shopped at least one of these malls including Hyper-star, Imtiaz, Dolmen Mall, Park Tower, Forum, Ocean Tower, and Emerald Tower. 230 people were targeted and their replies were included in the process of analysis.

11. Reliability Analysis

The reliability analysis is use to analyze that your scale variables are consistent or not. Cronbach Alpha is most common measure of reliability. Overall reliability was checked on the data of 230 respondents. Since the value in column is 0.916, which is ≥ 0.6 it means that, our data and the scale is reliable.

12. Regression Analysis

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.703 ^a	.494	.483	.52276

a. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson, Promotional Signage, Window Display, In-store Display

Table 2: ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.216	4	13.054	47.768	.000 ^a
	Residual	53.563	196	.273		
	Total	105.780	200			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Salesperson, Promotional Signage, Window Display, In-store Display

b. Dependent Variable: Impulse Buying

From the ANOVA table we had found that the P Value is less than 0.05 which is significant evident for us to state that all the independent variables (Salesperson, Promotional Signage, Window Display, In-store Display) are influencing or have 48.3% impact on dependent variable which is impulse buying. 48.3%, here is the value taken from the model summary, which is adjusted R^2 value. **Hair et al**, (2014) considered R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 for the dependent variables as substantial, moderate, and weak, respectively

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.340	.221		1.541	.125
Window Display	.136	.055	.168	2.442	.015
In-store Display	.283	.081	.256	3.508	.001
Promotional Signage	.337	.062	.345	5.462	.000
Sales Personal behavior	.074	.056	.085	1.328	.186

a. Dependent Variable: Impulse Buying

Since the Significance value is less than 0.05 and secondly the absolute value of T for window display is greater than two, therefore, we have sufficient evident that window display has an impact on impulse buying by 13.6%. It means that if Window Display is increased by 1 Store Switching Behavior would increase by 0.136. Similarly the Significance value for in-store display is less than 0.05 and Moreover the absolute value of T for In-store Display is greater than 2 therefore we have sufficient evident that In-store Display has an impact on impulse buying by 28.3%. It means if In-store Display is increased by 1 Store Switching Behavior would increase by 0.283. Going towards the Value of Coefficients of Beta for Promotional Signage has the same case that its value is significant at 95% confidence level and greater than 2 at the absolutely value of T, so we have sufficient evident that promotional Signage has an impact on impulse buying by 33.7%. It means if Promotional Signage is increased by 1 Store Switching Behavior would increase by 0.337. The Only Variable Sales Personal Behavior's Significance Value is greater than 0.05 and its less than 2 for T-value. Hence we would say that Sales Personal Behavior does not have any impact on Impulse Buying Behavior. Here the Value described in the above statement for Beta Coefficient is Unstandardized Value of Beta.

13. Discussion

Impulse buying is an unexpected and instant buying with no previous intentions to buy (rook, 1987). The research has identified the four external factors window display, in-store Display, promotional signage and sales personal behavior are influencing the impulse buying behavior of consumer. The research attempts to identify the relationship between all four independent variable and dependent variables. The results showed that all factor excluding sales personal behavior have an impact on impulse buying. It also showed that there is a correlation between sale personnel behavior but it is a weak positive correlation and its value is 0.463 and on the other hand the P Value of Beta coefficient which is 0.186 greater than 0.05 is an evident for accepting the H_0 : that sales personnel behavior has no any significant impact on impulse buying behavior. The study further suggested that when customer came across to the above-defined factors, there are greater chances that they would purchase the product based on impulse behavior. Moreover it suggest that window display, promotional signage, In-store display serves as the event that create a desire that at the end encourages a shopper to take the buying decision based on impulse. According to MacInnis & Price (1987) and Sherry (1990) searching for product or purchasing a product without prior decision to purchase, gives interesting shopping experience that is enjoyable. Furthermore, Beatty & Ferrell (1998) suggested in their research that propensity of impulse buying affect in-store surfing positively.

14. Conclusion

In conclusion, of all the finding we can say that all independent factors (window display, promotional signage, In-store display, and sales personnel behavior) have an impact on dependent variable (impulse buying behavior). However, if these factors are used combination of two, three or all at ones they can affect the impulse buying behaviors of shoppers. Darden et al., (1983) studied the correlation between physical attractions of Malls/retail store, results reveled that eye-catching display had a greater correlation than a variety of goods. Moreover results suggest that the more the eye catchy window display a store have the more chances that customer may step in. so, it creates the implication for retailers to make their store outer look so attractive that customer get attracted towards the store. The

sales personnel behavior too can boost the sales of store. Think of the store where all the staff is well dresses and behaving with you in very gentle way you would probably want to go the same store next time. According to Kim (2003), vivid and clear shelf placement plays an important role in the sales of a product. The research says that when customer moves through the aisle of store the product seems to be blurry until there is a large amount of same product is placed together. Eye level is buy level shelf placement too plays an important role in impulse buying. An impulse buying practice, which gives positive experiences, helps to develop store trustworthiness, loyalty, and customer pleasure, satisfaction, and perceived value affects the futures purchase choices.

15. Recommendations

Study has shown that Impulse buying is affected by external factors, but we cannot deny to the fact that it is more related to emotions/attitudes and affective reactions. The emotional part is to a certain extent very tough to conclude by the quantitative investigation. For this reason, a combo of qualitative and quantitative techniques of research such as experiments and observations suggested for the future examination of the topic. In today's world, impulse purchase is a phenomenology of contemporary society. It is the same case with Pakistan, the malls and retail outlets are the novel concept for the society people are more interested in buying and visiting to these store rather purchasing from a local market. Due to the constraints of time and budgeting, this research is limited to the metropolitan city of Pakistan (Karachi), but other researcher can expand the research in many other cities of Pakistan at large level. The study only discusses the Impulsive buying patterns of urban population so the impulsive buying patterns of rural customers/population are still uncovered. Further, the researchers can do the research in rural areas to identify the impulsiveness in rural population in order to develop a new aspect of impulsiveness.

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